

TINCTORIAL AFFINITY FLUCTUATES IN THE TUNE OF ENVIRONMENTAL TEMPERATURE CORROBORATING THE SECRETORY DYNAMICS OF THE CEREBRAL NEUROSECRETORY ELEMENTS IN *LYMNAEA (RADIX) LUTEOLA* WITH REFERENCE TO PERFORMIC ACID – ALCIAN BLUE

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ABSTRACT

The investigation reveals the adoption of method Performic Acid – Alcian Blue yields a good positive result of the cerebral ganglionic neurosecretory elements of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* exposed to various temperatures. Incidentally a good positive intensity of the stain is being elicited when the animals are kept in the different fluctuating temperature regimes ([low (4°C, 10°C), near ambient (20°C, 25°C) and high (30°C, 35°C)] on their secretory dynamics. Side by side, the histochemical nature of the neurosecretory material has also been recorded. In all the profiles of study individuals exposed to near ambient temperature are being considered as normal. And finally, the histochemical analyses are made under different temperature regimes on the cerebral neurosecretory elements to ascertain correlative biochemical changes.

KEYWORDS: Performic Acid –Alcian Blue (PAAB), Neurosecretory materials (NSM), Secretory dynamics, Palkovit's formula, Hypo-Hyper & Near ambient temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

Protein components of Neurosecretory materials (NSM) probes to be ubiquitous and possibly the term Peptidergic neurons is apparently applied in both vertebrates and invertebrates. Several investigators successfully demonstrated the proteinaceous compound in the NSM in several invertebrates with adoption of Performic Acid – Alcian Blue (PAAB) method. Available literature on the biochemical nature of NSM elaborated in molluscs and other invertebrates reveal that bioactive molecules are basically peptides.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The materials used in the present investigation are full grown *Lynaea (Radix) luteola* size ranging from 1.2 cm to 1.5 cm. Individual specimens are subjected to different temperature regimes- Near Ambient, hypo and hyperthermal conditions in separate B.O.D. Chambers.

HISTOPHYSIOLOGICAL STUDIES

Investigations were made on the basis of staining intensities, of features morphological stainable granules, their quantity and distribution, size of the cell bodies and nuclei in terms of volume determination by using Palkovit's formula (1963). The activity of the cells in question were assessed as per the formulation devised by Hartwick-nucleoplasmic indices (Np index)-cited by De Robertis (1968). Incidentally, the cells of either large or medium dimensions are taken into account for the diagnosis of their criteria.

GENERAL HISTOCHEMISTRY

Performic Acid – Alcian Blue method (Adams and Sloper, 1956) for cystine. Fixative-Carnoy's fluid.

OBSERVATIONS

PERFORMIC ACID - ALCIAN BLUE REACTION (PAAB)

1. HYPOTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 4°C

Localisation of AB-positive material within the neurosecretory perikarya is not clear and hence, very weak reaction is portrayed (Fig.1). Critical examination, however, reveals thin distribution of fine cystine particles. Sometimes these granules may be detected along the axon-hillock regions. A little variations of such reaction has also been visualized amongst the types of cell in question. In any case, the response to the reaction is not so sharp despite the fact that their (AB-granules) distribution is not ruled out.

Fig. 1. Neurosecretory cells showing very weak PAAB-reaction for the localisation of dithio-groups. Note a faint reaction at the axon-hillock region of some large cells. X 125.

AT 10°C

Intensity of reaction is relatively strong (Fig. 2). Nucleus along with its intracellular material shows light affinity for alcian blue reaction. The cytoplasm is found to contain cystine positive materials more often. But morphological features of secretory granules are not that clear. Characteristically, localisation of the stained granules along a few axonal processes may be traced when observed critically.

Fig. 2. Section showing strong reaction for the distribution of alcian blue positive substances within the cytoplasm. Note cystine positive materials along the axonal process of some NSCs. X 125.

2. EXPOSURE TO NEAR AMBIENT TEMPERATURE

AT 20°C

Most of the neuroendocrine elements are in the possessions of AB-positive material. But there exists a gradation to their reactivity which may be subscribed on the basis of the synthetic rhythm of the cell concerned (Fig, 3). Nuclei are, in general, poor to the tinctorial response. On some occasions, the cytoplasm are endowed with granular material which often concentrate in the vicinity of the nuclei. Evidence are there where the apex of the cell may contain moderate distribution of AB-positive granules and gradually undergo waning at the posterior half of the cell concerned. Axonal processes ordinarily do not show indication for AB-positive distribution.

Fig. 3. Section showing weak to moderate reaction amongst the to the neurosecretory elements with reference possession of PAAB-positive granules. Note axonal processes without discrete PAAB-positive granules. X 125.

AT 25°C

Localisation of AB-positive substances within the perikarya, irrespective of their cell types, reflects heterogeneous profile. Indeed, variation in the distribution of dithio-groups amongst the cell types is rather spectacular (Fig. 4). The nuclei are very weak to this reaction and accordingly the intranuclear material undergo faint colouration. Sometimes, the presence of AB-positive material in the vicinity of the axon hillock and as well as along the axonal tract may be ascertained.

Fig. 4. Section demonstrating some of the neurosecretory elements having variable quanta of dithio-groups. X 125.

3. HYPERTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 30°C

Presence of cystine-positive material within the neurosecretory perikarya is observed. Here also fluctuation in their amount is understood which obviously marks the secretory dynamics (Fig. 5). Cells of smaller dimension, on some occasion, may show more accumulation of AB-positive material under light cytoplasmic background. Normally, the nuclei are less responsive. Evidence for the migration of AB-positive material along the axonal processes are not ruled out.

Fig. 5. Section revealing gradation in the distribution of PAAB-positive granules within the cytoplasm. Note evidence for the migration of these materials along the axonal processes. X 125.

AT 35°C

Localisation of AB-positive material is clear (Fig. 6) and is evident in case of cells having medium to smaller dimension. The nucleoli are conspicuous and remain in sharp contrast with other intranuclear materials. Cytoplasm often bear AB-reactive substances and are observed in greater abundance than what is found in the preceding hyperthermic individuals exposed at 30°C. Interestingly, as it appears, the dispatch of AB-positive granules along the axonal course maintains a direct relationship the quanta with of alcian blue positive particles possessed by the perikarya in question.

Fig. 6. Section showing clear exposition of PAAB-positive material and their subsequent disposition along the axonal processes. X 125.

Table 1: Showing alterations in the histochemical profiles of cerebral neurosecretory cells of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* under the variable temperature regimes.

Methods adopted	Reacting sites/groups	Hypothermal		Near Ambient		Hyperthermal	
		4° C	10° C	20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C
Performic Acid - Alcian Blues (PAAB)	S-S group	+/-	+++	+/-	+/-	+++	+++

+/- Doubtful reaction

+///+/// Reactions of increasing intensity

Series 1,2: Reactions of increasing intensity

Series 3: Doubtful reaction intensity of Performic Acid - Alcian Blue (PAAB) reaction is well documented in the Hypothermal and Near Ambient temperatures but in the hyperthermal situation the same intensity dwindles.

DISCUSSION

Histochemical evidence highlighted by previous investigators (Sloper, 1957; Lake, 1970) provide clue polypeptide endowed more with cystine (SS) irrespective of vertebrates or invertebrates. Indeed, most of the Gomori-positive NSCs in several invertebrate (Dogra, 1968; Faruqi, 1977 and Awasthi, 1982) contained protein rich in cystine (SS) and cysteine (SH). Richness of disulphide groups in the protein component of NSM has been assessed (Dogra, 1968) in view of the existence of 'level substances' from which the active hormonal principle (S) may be cleaved in the event of 'release' (Bem, 1962). Secretory neurons in the cerebral ganglion of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* responded moderate to weak. Sometimes near negative response has been elicited. Such situation is more spectacular under the ambient temperature. This is rather intriguing. But both at lower and higher thermal exposures such trend is somewhat changed and moderate to near moderate response has been reflected. Fluctuating reacting response is recorded earlier under different "environmental circumstances" (Decastro and Rodrigo, 1979) and this may be interpreted in the light of cytochemical analysis of the NSCs in *P. boraceiensis*. Furthermore, variable 'sulphur-pool' available within the secretory perikarya (Steel and Morris, 1975) may be considered in this context when quantification of "metabolic enzymes" under variable thermal exposition that works on neuroendocrine system in the long run (Ochrieng' -Odero, 1992) is adhered to.

There exists a parallelism between the distribution of neuro-secretory substances and conventionally stained material distributed within the cytoplasm of neurosecretory perikarya.

To determine biochemical criteria of these conventionally stained material histochemical tests are indispensable for the unique identifiable cum 'varsatile' neurons. Several histochemical tests namely, alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, PAS-reactive substances, SBB-reaction masked lipids, MBB-reactive substances and or localisation of distribution of dithio groups are adopted under variable temperature regimes. (Nanda et. al., 2023,2024).

Incidentally, hypothermic and hyperthermic conditions render fluctuating trend in the localisation of these reactive substances. Various factors like intracellular enzymic activity, metabolic enzymes, macromolecular interference, tempo of synthetic rhythms, formation of are "labile barrier", protein protein synthetic ability and sulphur pool considered in the context of "environmental circumstances" for the exothermic species under study. Overall survey portrays that the neurosecretory material are histochemically rich in carbohydrates, protein bound aminogroups and glycoproteins and lipids. And likely that these criteria may subject to gradations in accordance with the variable thermal expositions which subsequently tell upon the neuroendocrine system in the long run.

Conclusive Remark

Effects of both high and low thermal exposures encompass some salient changes with respect to the abundance substances, electron dense granules and their disposition within the of heterochromatin microtubular processes, appearances of the cytoplasmic fibrillar elements etc. Such changes from one temperature regime to other provide clues to ascertain the structure-function relationship in the context of the secretory behaviour of the cells concerned. This is specially pertinent when environmental flux in the natural habitat of the species under study is considered (Nanda et. al., 2023).

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